

**IN THE STUDY OF MEDICAL HELMINTHOLOGY, THE
NEGATIVE CONSEQUENCES OF ASCARIASIS DISEASE ARE THE
FREQUENCY OF OCCURRENCE AMONG THE POPULATION AND
MEASURES to INTRODUCE PREVENTION METHODS INTO THE
POPULATION**

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Annotation: Currently, helminths are distinguished from common parasites found among people in almost all layers of the Earth's surface. Helminths have been causing several negative consequences in the body, mainly damaging the small intestine of the human body. Parasitised bat species are called "helminths". The science that studies helminths is helminthology and the diseases they cause are called helminthoses. Sexually mature parasitic flies, called helminths, parasitize mainly in vertebrates. Many of them parasitize endoparasites, that is, in various internal organs of the animal and human organism. Helminths are divided into biogelminths and geogelminths according to their development cycle. Intermediate or additional bosses are involved in the development cycle of biogelmints, as an example of biogelmints we can do with liverworm and example.

Keywords: Parasitology, nematode, helminth, biogelment, geogelment, enzyme.

Human ascarida (*Ascaris lumbricoides*). Human ascariasis is distributed on Earth in almost all countries. In some countries, for example, in Japan, almost all of akholi is infected with a soldier. Because, in agriculture in Japan, human excretion is widely used as an organic fertilizer in areas where vegetable and ground crops are planted. The soldier has some Sexes, the male is much shorter than the female, that is, the male is 15-25 cm long, and the female is 25-40 CM. In addition in the male soldier, the hip and tail will be spirally twisted to the side of the abdomen. The female, on the other hand, has a large body and a straight tail. At the front end of the worm is a mouth with three lips, in which there will be suckers that the very small eye does not progress. Before reaching the next end of the body, on the side of the abdomen is the posterior outlet hole. The next part of this hole is the tail. The genital organs have a simple 60 structure. In males, the genital opening is located near the posterior end of the body. It consists of only one tube that extends inside. The sexual orifice of females opens in the anterior half of the body, outwards by the abdomen.

A single flute runs through this hole, which does not extend far and splits into two branches. The thin filamentous end of the branches is called the ovary, the part that gradually becomes larger is called the egg path, and the most large is called the uterus. In the soldier parasitizes the small intestine of a person. A person with a soldier in the intestine is considered a source that infects and spreads the parasite. One female lays up to 200-250 thousand eggs in a soldier overnight (one soldier lives at least 200 days), and several 10 million during her life. lays eggs. The main difference between ascarida and other helminths is that three floors over the egg will be surrounded by a pod, but a newly laid, that is, a soldier who has just come out of a sick person will not have the opportunity to damage his egg, it is necessary to have 15-25 days outside in a humid environment, during which a larva with A human soldier develops without an intermediate master, that is, the only master is a person. In the external environment, the soldier can keep his egg viable for up to 10 years. Such an egg with a larva inside is infected by a person by eating unboiled water, unwashed vegetables-fruits, especially strawberries, foods that remain open on top. The veil of an egg that has fallen into the stomach dissolves under the influence of gastric juices (enzymes), while the larva moves through the intestinal wall into the blood, migrating for 10 days, going around to the liver, heart, lungs. When the larva arrives in the lungs, there is a change in a person, such as the phenomenon of pulmonary colds, a cough appears, and when coughing, pain appears in the lungs, chest, at certain times the temperature rises. When coughing, the larvae come up through the bronchi and thyme, that is, into the oral cavity. When swallowed again with saliva from there, the larvae fall through the stomach into the small intestine, clinging to its walls and turning into an adult soldier for 2.5 months. They hatch in time and lay eggs again. Ascarids feed on foods and vitamins that are most valuable for the human body in the intestine, causing avitaminosis in humans, as a result of which a person becomes susceptible to various other infectious diseases. The disease caused by ascarids is called ascariidosis. From this disease, a person experiences low blood clots, nausea, vomiting, loss of appetite, etc. Sometimes ascarida pass from the intestine to the gallbladder and block it. From the intestines, the stomach, esophagus, Hatto can go to the respiratory tract. In addition, the soldier poisons the human body by extracting toxic substances from himself. A thousand years ago, the Byzantine doctor Eginsky described the condition of patients with ascariidosis as follows: "people with ascarids in the intestines feel pain in the intestines and stomach, dry cough, sometimes hiccups. In his sleep, there is a state of severe beating of the heart, chills and shouts, then the patient goes to sleep again. The children, for no reason, emit a rumbling tongue, gnaw their teeth, sit quietly with their eyes

closed, they are very upset if their peace is broken. Sometimes ascarida become nauseous if they get into the stomach, cause barking pain and disgust with food. When patients with ascariidosis are forced to eat, they barely swallow food, often there are many cases of throwing back

In Uzbekistan, there are frequent cases of ascariidosis between akholi, who live in Mountain and mountainous regions. Akholi's pain with ascariidosis varies between 1-90% of the population. For Example, A. According to Mansurov, in 1968, among akholi living in the Bostanlyk District of the Tashkent region, children suffered from ascariidosis in 57.2 percent and adults - 33.9 percent. Ascarids are particularly common in children. The poison of human ascariidosis has a particularly bad effect on the body of children. The infected child has a sore head, turns his head, becomes restless at night, whispers and gnaws at his teeth. Because the pain is intermittent, the doctor often also suspects appendicitis. Usually, several, sometimes dozens, hundreds of ascarids parasitize in the human intestine. It is known to have been found in 900 of a single man and another in 5,126 of his soldiers. In such cases, ascarids wound the intestinal wall, clogged in the intestines and did not pass food. Occasional cases of liver and brain failure have also been observed that have left a person dead. People with ascariidosis are treated with medications such as piperazine, adipinate, decaris (levamisole), naphthamon (alco-par, mebendazole), vermorin. Treatment will definitely need to be carried out under the supervision of a doctor.

CONCLUSION

To avoid ascarida, it is first necessary to thoroughly treat all the patients who have succumbed to it. In each apartment, in public places, there should be a closed-type hostel, which is littered with waste. Non-contaminated human excreta should not be used as fertilizer for gardens and crops. Before eating raw vegetables, whole fruits and cereals, you need to wash them with vodka or boiled or running water. In order to keep food and dishes from flies, it is necessary to keep them indoors, apply anti-fly measures and, of course, observe the rules of personal hygiene. Some species of ascarids also parasitize livestock and poultry. For example, pigs are parasitized by the pig ascarid, chickens are parasitized by the chicken ascarid, horses are parasitized by the horse ascarid, sheep are parasitized by the sheep soldier, cattle are parasitized by the cattle neoascariid. In addition, the dangers of ascariidosis, the negative consequences of which are due to the implementation of the necessary knowledge for the population in the Departments of the neighborhood office by the chief Doctors of the family polyclinic.

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